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"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

#STI2022GRX

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#STI22GRX

On the impact of geo-contextualized and local research in the global North and South¹

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Introduction

The title can be considered the most important summary of a research article: it can describe its methods, design, and main findings or reveal important contextual specifications of the research (Diener, 1984). However, some authors may choose to decontextualize their work by using more generic or bold titles. A recent study by Castro Torres and Alburez-Gutierrez (2022) shows that social sciences studies using data from the global North (Europe and North America) are less likely to contextualize their title than studies from the global South. The authors conclude that this omission of geo-contextualization from the global North could potentially constitute an unwarranted claim on universality and may, in turn, lead to lesser recognition and impact of global South studies. However, Castro Torres and Alburez-Gutierrez did not analyze citations to verify this hypothesis.

Past bibliometric studies have investigated the relationship between titles' characteristics (e.g., titles' lengths, presence of non-alphanumeric characters or rarely used words) and the scholarly impact of an article (Buter & van Raan, 2011; Falagas et al., 2013; Thelwall, 2017). No clear tendencies were found in these studies. Past studies suggest that the presence of specific contextualization in the title, such as a country name (Paiva et al., 2012; Rostami et al., 2014; Jacques & Sebire, 2010; Abramo, D'Angelo & Di Costa, 2016, Mongeon et al., 2017) or a specific organism (Burns, 2015) is associated with fewer citations, although Nair and Gibbert (2016) diverged from other studies by finding no significant effect.

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Some limitations of these past studies include the use of small samples (a few hundred publications), the focus on specific countries or disciplines, and the lack of control for other variables to isolate the relationship between geo-contextualization and citations. They also used country names to identify geo-contextualized research, which risks producing false negatives when other types of geographical entities (e.g., city names, states, and other topological features) are used in the articles. This work-in-progress aims to overcome these limitations by analyzing a large multidisciplinary dataset using an extended list of geographical markers to improve the identification of location references in articles and by considering both geo-contextualized and local research. Articles are considered *geo-contextualized* when a geographical reference is mentioned in the title or abstract and *local* when the country of affiliation of one of the authors matches the country of the location mentioned in the title or abstract. Our research questions are:

1. How is geo-contextualized research distributed across fields and the global North and South?
2. How does geo-contextualizing relate to research impact?
3. How does the citation (dis)advantage of local research vary by country?

Data and Methods

All articles and reviews (n=29,850,298) published between 1997 and 2020 indexed in the Web of Science (WoS) were collected. We used the OECD classification to group publications by field. The minor OECD fields were used to normalize citation scores, but we used the six major fields for reporting our findings. Publications were assigned to the global South and global North based on the country of the affiliations². A publication with authors from both groups is assigned to both groups and weighed by the proportion of affiliation from each region. Table 1 displays the number of publications included in our analysis by field and region.

Table 1. Number of publications in the dataset

Field	Publications		
	North	South	Total
Natural Sciences	2,991,885	3,354,526	6,346,411
Engineering and Technology	1,756,567	1,695,050	3,451,617
Medical and health science	8,692,157	1,335,589	10,027,746
Agricultural sciences	6,896,250	298,005	7,194,255
Social sciences	653,893	199,668	853,561
Humanities	580,153	47,250	627,403
All fields	21,570,905	6,930,089	28,500,994

We used the spaCy Python package to perform named entity recognition and identify locations in the titles or abstracts. The analysis initially yielded 4,372,907 mentions of locations in titles

² The list of countries belonging to the global north and south was obtained here: <https://worldpopulationreview.com/country-rankings/global-south-countries>. Mexico was manually added to that list of Global South countries.

and 17,707,922 in abstracts. We eliminated false positives by mapping the identified locations to the GeoNames geographical database, which contains over eleven million location names covering all countries. From there, we were able to associate a country with each entity. When an entity matched several entries from more than one country in the GeoNames database, we assigned the country of the entry with the highest population. Overall, we could associate a single country with 109,237 entities mentioned more than 12 million times in more than 5 million publications.

Results

Figure 1 presents the share of publications that are geo-contextualized and local by each OECD field. Globally, less than 17% of publications mentioned a geographical location in their title or abstract and less than 7% are considered local research. In most fields, geo-contextualized publications from the global South represent a more significant share than those from the global North. However, in Social Sciences and Humanities, it is the opposite.

Figure 1. Number and share of articles mentioning a geographical location by discipline in the global North and global South.

Figure 2 presents the mean normalized citation score (MNCS) for geo-contextualized and local research, by region and discipline. Publications with affiliations from the global South have a citation disadvantage in all fields, except in Engineering and Technology. This citation disadvantage is even stronger for geo-contextualized publications from the global South. However, this trend seems reverse when considering local research on the global South.

Figure 2. Mean normalized citation score by region and discipline for all publications, geo-contextualized research (geo) and local research (local)

Figure 3 displays, for each field, the top 15 producers of local research in raw publications numbers, ranked by MNCS for the local research paper. While countries from the global North dominate, which is unsurprising given that countries were included based on publication counts, it is remarkable that several countries from the global South made the top 15. However, we can see that, except for China, local research produced in the global South tends to have a lower citation impact than local research produced in the North.

Figure 3. Top 15 producers of local research in each discipline and MNCS of that research

Discussion and conclusion

Building on the preliminary findings presented here, this work will be developed further by including additional cleaning of location names to improve country assignment. Further analysis of the results by specific country, discipline, and evolution over time, will allow a deeper understanding of the extent to which researchers around the globe engage in local research and geo-contextualize their work in their titles and abstracts. For now, our study found that a small portion of research can be identified as geo-contextualized or local and that, in most fields, publications from the global South make up the larger share of the geo-contextualized work, which also comes with a citation disadvantage. Our results will hopefully contribute to discussions about the growing importance given to local research by funders and other research governance entities and the challenges that this may bring to researchers who must adapt to such a local context while competing in a global research system.

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